

Advancing shared visions for Arctic observing: A brief status assessment of RNA CoObs and ArcticPASSION projects' contribution to SAON Arctic ROADS

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Background and overview

The Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) initiative of the Arctic Council and the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) developed an Arctic Roadmap for Observing and Data Systems (Arctic ROADS) to promote and facilitate observing efforts that yield tangible benefits for Indigenous Peoples of the Arctic and broader society. SAON's vision for Arctic ROADS was a topic of discussion and refinement at the Arctic Observing Summit (AOS) in 2018 (see timeline in Fig. 1). The 2018 Arctic Science Ministerial in Berlin, Germany helped build support for the implementation of this vision through a small number of demonstration activities.

Specifically, two projects, the Research Networking Activity for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs) and the Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems Implementing Observations for Societal Needs (Arctic PASSION; see also the AOS Whitepaper on "Visions and Policy recommendations for a future Arctic Observing System of Systems" by Arctic PASSION), were supported by the U.S. National Science Foundation and the European

Horizon 2020 program, respectively. A key element of both projects was to implement Arctic ROADS and its four component steps, including the establishment of Arctic ROADS Expert Panels (EP) (Starkweather et al., 2021).

This AOS 2026 White Paper provides a brief perspective and status report of these activities to inform discussions at the Summit. A longer publication summarizing this work is in preparation for an Arctic PASSION special issue of the journal *Ambio*.

Fig. 1: Timeline of SAON Arctic ROADS and key supporting events that led to implementation activities described in this contribution.

From SAON Arctic ROADS planning to the establishment of pilot EPs

The SAON Arctic ROADS process recognizes four guiding principles (Starkweather et al., 2021):

1. Indigenous Peoples' equitable partnership and funding for their active participation are critical to the ROADS process;
2. All aspects of the ROADS process should support broadly shared benefits from the observing and data systems;
3. The ROADS process should complement and integrate, without duplication, the current planning approaches used by existing networks, activities and projects;
4. The ROADS process should support stepwise development through a flexible and evolving structure that allows grassroots identification of themes, infrastructures, and regional foci.

SAON leadership and the Arctic ROADS Advisory Panel (AP) have translated these guiding principles into a four-step process (Table 1) leading to output that supports and embodies a polycentric approach in the design and implementation of Arctic observing systems, with multiple centers of authority or leadership nodes working towards a common goal (Starkweather

et al., 2021). It is noteworthy that this process builds on concepts developed within the climate and ocean observing community for essential climate or ocean variables (e.g., Martín Miguez et al., 2026). Necessarily, ROADS expands and adapts these to Arctic settings where Indigenous rightsholders, recognition of teleconnections between the Arctic and lower latitudes, and an increasing range of potentially conflicting uses of Arctic environments are best addressed by co-design, co-production and equitable approaches.

Table 1: Four steps of the SAON ROADS Process

Step	Activities and output
1: Assemble the expert panel	Identify a core theme around a societal challenge, invite experts spanning a range of perspectives, draft an overview of the effort and the larger societal issues relevant to the theme.
2: Identify societal benefits and information use cases	Use a societal benefit assessment framework to identify the specific ways information related to the theme is or could be used and link these use cases to larger societal benefits. Select Shared Arctic Variables, these are observables that address information needs across benefit areas.
3: Specify observational, data, and information product requirements for those use cases	For each use case identified in Phase 2, the expert panel identifies necessary requirements with regard to observations (e.g., frequency, type, or coverage of measurements), data systems (e.g., sharing and data sovereignty concerns), and information (e.g., higher-level products for distribution).
4: Implementation plan	Compile a report outlining what observations are already available, identifying where relatively easy efforts could bring existing observations in line with the requirements, and securing commitments from observers to meeting the requirements.

A core thread of activities by Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs is the support of 6 EPs focusing on 5 themes of (i) permafrost, (ii) sea ice, (iii) wildfire, (iv) salmon, and (v) harmful algal blooms (HABs), with each project supporting three of these (Table 2). In following the broader SAON

Arctic ROADS principles, the five themes were identified and couched in terms of shared Arctic variables (SAVs). For details on SAVs, derived from and expanding the essential variables concept, see Bradley et al. (2022). At the time of the AOS 2026, only the European Wildfire EP has reached Phase 4 (Implementation) of the ROADS process. Its North American complement, currently in Phase 1, has been established to provide a different regional perspective on wildfires and explore how to expand from the local or regional scale of specific pilot EPs.

The Salmon EP, established based on guidance emerging out of the Arctic Observing Summit’s Food Security Working Group, focused on the Pacific Arctic sector (specifically Chinook salmon in Bristol Bay, Alaska) in light of the recent Alaska/Canada Chinook salmon decline and the ensuing food security crisis (DeMaster et al., 2025). The challenges in the policy and regulatory environment, including Indigenous sovereignty over subsistence and cultural practices, required an extended period of time to establish trust among the diverse participants of this panel. Now that a group has been convened that represents the full breadth of rights and interests in the region, Phase 3 of the ROADS process is nearing completion.

Table 2: Summary of SAON Arctic ROADS EPs (Completed phases as of December 2025 shown in grey; blue: Arctic PASSION support; green: RNA CoObs support)
 [Note that the Wildfire SAV is covered by a European (EU) and a North American (NA) EP]

Expert Panel	Phase I: assemble EP	Phase 2: societal benefits and use cases	Phase 3: observational, data, and information product requirements	Phase 4: implementation	Funding
Permafrost					EU
Sea Ice					EU, Canadian government
EU Wildfire					EU
NA Wildfire					NSF, AMAP, Arctic PASSION
Salmon					NSF, Sasakawa Peace Foundation
Harmful algal blooms					NSF, NOAA

Engaging with observing efforts outside of the immediate SAON & Arctic ROADS circle

In supporting Arctic ROADS process, both RNA CoObs and Arctic PASSION also reached out to observing initiatives outside of the core circle of European and North American constituent

organizations. Two groups with which closer engagement was sought include Asian, specifically Japanese researchers, and community-based monitoring efforts.

For Asian researchers, exemplified by Japan's Arctic Challenge for Sustainability (ArCS) II program, it was found that, in theory, engagement with the Arctic ROADS process was best advanced by actively participating in the initiation of EPs. In practice, the barriers both in aligning research planning in Japan with Arctic ROADS and in identifying promising candidate SAVs to build expert panels around proved to be significant. As an outcome of conversations at the AOS 2024, the idea for an EP focused on Arctic drivers of mid-latitude extreme weather events has emerged, but requires further action. The Salmon EP has involved Japanese researchers, given the importance of the Bering Sea for both North American and Asian salmon populations during their marine life stage. A promising avenue for greater cohesion and collaboration between Asian and European or North American efforts is the joint development of information portals that ideally draw on federated data archives (Lescak et al., 2026).

Community-based monitoring, exemplified within RNA CoObs by the Alaska Arctic Observatory and Knowledge Hub (AAOKH; Hauser et al., 2023), has the potential to contribute to the Arctic ROADS process by shifting research priorities from global, climate-scale observations toward local and regional phenomena and processes central to Indigenous communities' lifeways and priorities. This engagement is best facilitated through the selection of community representatives who can serve as boundary spanners through their membership in ROADS EPs. Such involvement, explored by the Sea Ice EP led out of the Canadian component of Arctic PASSION, can further support the process by integrating local and regional-scale information sharing into open-access data archives, and by advancing practical applications such as ice hazard assessments.

RNA CoObs and Arctic PASSION perspectives on Arctic ROADS

SAON's Arctic ROADS process has been envisioned as supporting polycentric approaches to sustained observations of a changing Arctic (Starkweather et al., 2021), allowing for multiple centers of authority and action that work towards a common goal. The outcome of such efforts is coordinated data and information products – emerging from distributed observational programs operated by a range of actors, agencies, and institutions – that serve the needs of Arctic Indigenous Peoples and communities while also providing broader societal benefits to Arctic and non-Arctic nations. By initiating half a dozen pilot EPs, Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs explored strengths and weaknesses of such an approach for a subset of SAVs. The mix of methods employed in standing up and facilitating EPs (e.g., one or two facilitators leading the panel vs. a larger steering group; drawing on an AOS Working Group to identify target SAVs vs. taking up guidance from government agencies on observing gaps, etc.) highlighted the importance of careful selection of EP membership aligned with SAV information users. The diversity of approaches helped refine AP involvement and resources to guide EPs through

the four ROADS stages. Importantly, with Arctic Council Working Groups and initiatives such as SAON on hiatus after Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022, the distributed leadership of EPs and broad membership across sectors provided the means to continue panel work and generate output – making a strong case for polycentric governance of Arctic ROADS and EPs, with bottom-up efforts able to compensate for temporary lack of capacity at higher levels.

Equitable engagement and support of Indigenous Peoples is a key element of Arctic ROADS, seeking to overcome more than a century of parallel but disjunct perspectives on the importance of systematic tracking of environmental processes and phenomena by Indigenous community members and Arctic researchers. The work by RNA CoObs and Arctic PASSION illustrated that for Arctic ROADS to be successful, it needs to engage numerous forms of expertise. These include Indigenous experts, funders, data experts, practitioners of observing, those working at the regional/international scale, representatives of observing initiatives (such as the Distributed Biological Observatories), social scientists for assessing benefits, policy experts, science communicators, coordinators/facilitators, and those sitting at the boundaries between these bodies of expertise. These experts require support for salary and travel to provide impactful input in the ROADS process at the right time and place. While the pilot projects provided significant support, there are still substantial gaps in expertise and a lack of a full-time staff to manage ROADS. It also highlights the time necessary to build the EPs and work through the different Phases, as only the EU Wildfire completed all four Phases of the ROADS process within the timeframe of RNA CoObs and Arctic PASSION.

A key aspect of RNA CoObs' support was the establishment of an Indigenous Liaison Team, rather than placing a major burden of identifying and facilitating equitable approaches onto a single person. Indigenous consultants and facilitators contributed to the process as well, helping lay the groundwork and facilitate difficult conversations and learning processes. In RNA CoObs' case, the latter stemmed partly from a rush – necessitated in part by the specific funding mechanism – to submit a proposal that would have benefited from further work with Indigenous partners. In order to ensure the EP was able to fully focus on their roles and responsibilities the Sea Ice Theme established a Steering Group that dealt with the administrative overhead associated with the ROADS process. For further information see the AOS Short Statement by the Steering Group entitled "Rethinking the Landscape: Sea Ice, Inuit Priorities and Scientific Observations in a Time of Change".

In the current climate, clearly communicating societal benefits and value is crucial to motivate investments into Arctic observing systems and coordination. Arctic ROADS supports individuals, communities and programs to develop these societal benefits to share them with national and international initiatives. The approaches currently utilized are drawing on the International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework within ROADS. During the past few years, the US Arctic Observing Network (US AON) has developed the BENEFIT Tool that a few EPs have used to assess the relative merit of different observations). Instead of economic or hazard mitigation benefits, the Salmon EP has drawn on a well-being framework (Donkersloot et al., 2020) to evaluate SAVs. More work is needed to develop use case examples that support bottom-up

input, interconnect different countries (e.g., fish migration between Japan/Korea to Alaska and pan-Arctic initiatives), cover different system components (observing versus modeling), and align with national and/or global frameworks (e.g., national research priorities, funding programs, global environmental issues). The shared benefits of ROADS SAVs can be utilized to advocate for pan-Arctic coordination for shared infrastructure, coordinated proposal submissions, and funding support for continued coordination efforts like SAON.

Identifying international, cross-cutting funding mechanisms in support of Arctic ROADS and the implementation of SAV observations remains a critical and underdeveloped task. Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs speak to the efficacy of the AOS in identifying critical information needs, followed by further vetting and prioritization in the context of the ASM that then leads to funding opportunities at the national or EU level. There are a few positive examples, developed out of the Arctic PASSION network, such as the follow up Horizon Europe funded project 'Beyond Arctic PASSION' supporting the further development of the SAON ROADS process, the Nordforsk-funded project 'SustainME' supporting the next steps of the Sea Ice SAV process and further national funding for the Wildfire SAV process from Finland. However, coordinated international funding announcements and allocation of funds supportive of co-production approaches that may require support of Indigenous participation during the proposal development phase remain challenging.

Arctic ROADS process development has been an experience of 'building the plane while we're flying it.' Rather than employing already established frameworks and processes, there has been iterative development of a process that provides an appropriate balance between structure and flexibility between the AP, EP, and the broader observing community. To bring the broader observing community together, the ROADS AP had to provide sufficient structure to guide EPs in good practices, while being flexible enough to handle different disciplines and cultural or political contexts. All of the EPs supported by Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs started before the completion of guiding documentation and processes for all four phases of ROADS. With pilot projects completing their work, an evaluation will help improve documentation and identify the most effective support mechanisms for new projects seeking to establish a particular SAV. Drawing on insights gained from the pilots, reduction of entry barriers and streamlining of the four stages of the ROADS process will be important as well. For the SAV concept to develop its full potential to empower Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents, also in light of the upcoming International Polar Year, the process needs to become lean and cost-effective to make it attractive for future EP teams and funding agencies.

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